

Xizhen Xue

[Google Scholar](#) [ResearchGate](#)

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name: Xizhen Xue **Birth:** 01/26/1997
SODA Group
Affiliation: School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering,
Nanyang Technological University.
Supervisor: Prof. Yan Xu.
Phone: (+86) 185-6196-4065 **Email:** xizhen.xue@foxmail.com
Interest: Battery energy storage (BES) stochastic planning and scheduling methods, BES degradation, integrated energy system, power market, approximate dynamic programming, distributed optimization.

EDUCATION BACKGROUND

Huazhong University of Science and Technology (HUST) **Wuhan, Hubei, China**
Ph.D. in Electrical Engineering 09/2019-06/2024
Supervisor: Prof. Jinyu Wen
Prof. Xiaomeng Ai and Prof. Jiakun Fang
• **Thesis:** Research on Real-time Energy Storage Scheduling Methods of Microgrid Based on Multi-type Approximate Dynamic Programming

Huazhong University of Science and Technology (HUST) **Wuhan, Hubei, China**
B.S. in Electrical Engineering 09/2015-06/2019
• **Ranking:** 10/380

WORK EXPERIENCE

Nanyang Technological University **Singapore**
Research Fellow in Electrical Engineering 07/2024-Now
Supervisor: Prof. Yan Xu
Conducted multi-disciplinary research with a focus on BES life degradation analysis and microgrid energy management system, including the following project:

- Physics and Knowledge Transfer-based Cognitive Digital Twin for Advanced Battery Analytics

Clarkson University **Potsdam, New York, USA**
Visiting Research Scholar in Electrical Engineering 05/2023-03/2024
Supervisor: Prof. Yazhou Jiang and Prof. Thomas H. Ortmeier
• **Focus:** BES scheduling considering life degradation and distributed BES scheduling

RESEARCH GRANT AND CONTRACTS

1. Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities, HUST 01/2022-12/2023
“Distributed Real-time Scheduling of Microgrid Based on Approximate Dynamic Programming”
Role and Award: Principal Investigator; \$5,570

PRIMARY RESEARCH EXPERIENCES

1. National Natural Science Foundation of China 09/2018-12/2020
“Robust Coordinate Planning Method of Energy Storage in Integrated Gas and Electrical System”
Research role and output: Student Member; 4 Journal Papers [1,6,8-9], 1 Conference Paper [12]
Main Works: 1) Stochastic real-time energy management of integrated energy systems (integrated heat and power system, integrated oil and power system, data center microgrid)
2) Multi-dimensional approximate dynamic programming algorithm for multi-energy synergy

2. National Natural Science Foundation of China

01/2022-06/2024

“Continuous-time Optimization Theory and Application in Load Aggregation Modeling and Optimization Scheduling”

Research role and output: Student Member; 5 Journal Papers [2-5,10]

Main Works:

- 1) Battery energy storage linear degradation model
- 2) Scheduling model to promote BES lifespan benefit
- 3) Distributed optimization of power system under uncertainties

3. Key-Area Research and Development Program of Guangdong Province, China

09/2019-06/2024

“Research and Engineering Demonstration of Key Technologies for Intelligent Coordinated Operation of Power Source, Network, Load, and Energy Storage in Guangdong Province”

Research role and output: Student Member→Student PI; 2 Journal Papers [1,3], 1 Conference Paper [14]

Main Works:

- 1) Joint regulating reserve deployment model of EV and CG
- 2) Scalable ADP algorithm for different EV clusters

4. Science and Technology Program of China Southern Grid

12/2020-12/2022

“Key Technologies and Planning Methods of Energy Storage for New Energy Consumption”

Research role and output: Student PI; 1 Journal Paper [11], 1 Conference Paper [15]

Main Works:

- 1) Analysis of wind/solar power spatio-temporal characteristic
- 2) Generation techniques for time series of wind/solar power output
- 3) Energy storage planning methods for new energy consumption
- 4) Comprehensive evaluation method for energy storage planning schemes

5. Science and Technology Program of State Grid Corporation of China

12/2021–Till Now

“Collaborative Configuration Method and Key Operation Technologies of Energy Storage Resources in Power System for Multiple Application Scenarios”

Research role and output: Student PI; 2 Journal Paper [7,10], 1 Conference Paper [16]

Main Works:

- 1) Power system chronological operation simulation
- 2) Coordinated configuration method for power-based and energy-based storage under power system normal operation scenarios.
- 3) Coordinated configuration method for stationary and mobile energy storage under power system extreme operation scenarios

PUBLICATIONS (FIRST AUTHOR)

• Journal Paper

- [1]. **Xizhen Xue**, Jiakun Fang, Xiaomeng Ai, Shichang Cui, Yazhou Jiang, Wei Yao, and Jinyu Wen, “A Fully Distributed ADP Algorithm for Real-time Economic Dispatch of Microgrid,” *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, Vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 513-528, 2024.
- [2]. **Xizhen Xue**, Jiakun Fang, Xiaomeng Ai, Yazhou Jiang, Shichang Cui, Thomas H. Ortmeier, and Jinyu Wen, “Continuous ADP Algorithm to Promote Multiple Battery Energy Storage Lifespan Benefit in Real-Time Scheduling,” *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, Vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 5744-5760, 2024.
- [3]. **Xizhen Xue**, Xiaomeng Ai, Jiakun Fang, Shichang Cui, Yazhou Jiang, Wei Yao, Zhe Chen, and Jinyu Wen. “Real-time Schedule of Microgrid for Maximizing Battery Energy Storage Utilization,” *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1356-1369, 2023.
- [4]. **Xizhen Xue**, Xiaomeng Ai, Jiakun Fang, Wei Yao, and Jinyu Wen, “Real-time Schedule of Integrated Heat and Power System: A Multi-dimensional Stochastic Approximate Dynamic Programming Approach,” *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, Vol. 134, no. 107427, 2022.
- [5]. **Xizhen Xue**, Jiakun Fang, Xiaomeng Ai, Shichang Cui, Mengyao Xu, Wei Yao, and Jinyu Wen, “Real-time Joint Regulating Reserve Deployment of Electric Vehicles and Coal-fired Generators Considering EV Battery Degradation Using Scalable Approximate Dynamic Programming,” *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, Vol. 140, no. 108017, 2022.
- [6]. **Xizhen Xue**, Xiaomeng Ai, Jiakun Fang, Shichang Cui, Yazhou Jiang, Yan Xu, Jinyu Wen, “Fully Decentralized Approximate Dynamic Programming for Stochastic Energy Management of A Networked Microgrid System,” *IEEE*

- [7]. Shengshi Wang, Lianyong Zuo, Miao Li, Qiao Wang, **Xizhen Xue***, Qicong Liu, Shuai Jiang, Jian Wang, and Xitong Duan. "The Data-driven Modeling of Pressure Loss in Multi-batch Re-2 fined Oil Pipelines with Drag Reducer Using Long Short-Term 3 Memory (LSTM) Network," *s*, 2021, 14(18): 5871. (通讯作者, SCI检索, 中科院四区, IF: 3.2)
- [8]. Yunyun Wu, Jiakun Fang, Xiaomeng Ai, **Xizhen Xue**, Shichang Cui, Xia Chen, and Jinyu Wen, "Robust Co-planning of AC/DC Transmission Network and Energy Storage Considering Uncertainty of Renewable Energy," *Applied Energy*, 2023, 339: 120933.
- [9]. Menglin Zhang, Qiuwei Wu, Jinyu Wen, **Xizhen Xue**, Zhongwei Lin, and Fang Fang, "MPC-based Real-time Optimal Operation of Integrated Electricity and Heat System with Large-scale Heat Pumps Providing Following and Regulating Reserves," *Energy*, vol. 237, 2021, no. 121606.
- [10]. Shengshi Wang, Jiakun Fang, Jianzhong Wu, Xiaomeng Ai, Shichang Cui, Yue Zhou, Wei Gan, **Xizhen Xue**, Danji Huang, Hongyu Zhang, Jinyu Wen, "Learning-based spatially-cascaded distributed coordination of shared transmission systems for renewable fuels and refined oil with quasi-optimality preservation under uncertainty," *Applied Energy*, vol. 381, 2025, no. 125085.

• Conference Paper

- [11]. **Xizhen Xue**, Xiaomeng Ai, Jiakun Fang, Wei Yao, Jinyu Wen, Hang Shuai, and Haibo He, "Real-time Energy Management for the Integrated Heat and Power System Using Approximate Dynamic Programming," *2020 IEEE Power & Energy Society General Meeting (PESGM 2020)*, Montreal, QC, Canada, pp. 1-5.
- [12]. Qianwei Zheng, Ju Liu, Dongjun Yang, **Xizhen Xue**, Jiakun Fang, Wei Yao, and Xiaomeng Ai, "A comprehensive decision-making method for coordinated transmission and distribution network planning," *8th Renewable Power Generation Conference (RPG 2019)*, Shanghai, China, pp. 1-6.
- [13]. Rongkang Zhao, **Xizhen Xue**, Haifeng Ye, Zili Xu, Zhi Li, and Xiaomeng Ai, "Trans-Regional Dispatch of Large-Scale Wind and Solar Power Generation Base," *2023 7th IEEE Conference on Energy Internet and Energy System Integration (EI2 2023)*, Hangzhou, China, pp. 1-6.
- [14]. Yunyun Wu, **Xizhen Xue**, Lingling Le, Xiaomeng Ai, and Jiakun Fang, "Real-time Energy Management of Large-scale Data Centers: A Model Predictive Control Approach," *2020 IEEE Sustainable Power and Energy Conference (iSPEC 2020)*, Chengdu, China, pp. 2695-2701.
- [15]. Xun Lu, Zhiyao Zhong, **Xizhen Xue**, Yunyun Wu, Xiaomeng Ai, and Jiakun Fang, "Optimal Real-time Operation Strategy of Microgrid with Power-to-Hydrogen Device: an ADP Approach," *2022 5th International Conference on Energy, Electrical and Power Engineering (CEEPE 2022)*, Chongqing, China, pp. 758-763.
- [16]. Yubin He, Shouyu Liang, Huijie Gu, Bao Li, Wenchao Li, Ruiqi Wang, **Xizhen Xue**, and Xiaomeng Ai, "Short-Term Stochastic Real-Time Schedule of Power System with Hybrid BESs," *2023 IEEE International Conference on Power Science and Technology (ICPST 2023)*, Kunming, China, 2023, pp. 657-662.

EXPERTISE

Language skills:	Written/oral English and native Chinese
Research tools:	1) Proficient in Matlab and Python programming 2) Good at mathematical modelling and optimization: MATPOWER, Gurobi, and Yalmip 3) Other applications: Microsoft office set, LaTeX, OriginLab

PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

Peer review service:	IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy, International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems
Volunteer:	2020 PES China Council; 2021 CIEEC